

**TECHNOLOGICAL PROFICIENCY AND PERFORMANCE OF SCIENCE
TEACHERS AMID COVID 19 PANDEMIC: BASIS FOR
PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 10

Pages: 1272-1285

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2430

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13861415

Manuscript Accepted: 08-26-2024

Technological Proficiency and Performance of Science Teachers amid Covid 19 Pandemic: Basis for Professional Development Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the technological proficiency of science teachers and their performance during the COVID-19 pandemic, serving as a basis for developing a professional development program for the 2023-2024 school year. The study specifically sought to answer the following questions: (1) What is the technological proficiency level of science teachers and administrators based on self-assessment in the areas of technology operations and concepts, planning and designing learning environments, assessment and evaluation, productivity and professional practice, and ethical, legal, and human issues? (2) Is there a significant difference between the assessments of science teachers and administrators on these aspects? (3) What is the performance level of science teachers based on their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) for the 2020-2021 school year? (4) Is there a significant relationship between technological proficiency and teacher performance? (5) What professional development program could be proposed based on the study results? The study employed a quantitative research design, utilizing statistical methods including the weighted mean, z-test, correlated t-test, and Pearson r to analyze the data. Findings revealed that science teachers' technological proficiency in all assessed areas was rated as Proficient. No significant difference was found between the assessments of teachers and administrators on the proficiency levels. Based on IPCRF results for the 2020-2021 school year, 82.5% of teachers received a Very Satisfactory rating, 10% were rated Outstanding, and 7.5% were rated Satisfactory. Additionally, no significant relationship was identified between technological proficiency and teacher performance. Based on these findings, a professional development program in the form of a seminar-workshop was proposed to further enhance the technological proficiency and performance of science teachers.

Keywords: *technological, proficiency, performance, pandemic, program*

Introduction

The acquisition of transversal competencies—critical and creative thinking, interpersonal and intrapersonal skills, global citizenship, media, and information technology—requires the use of technology. These abilities are necessary in the modern world in order to prosper and be productive. Teaching and learning must therefore be reinvented and rethought. Consequently, the educational landscape is rapidly and profoundly being shaped by the technological learning environment. An essential part of the educational system is played by teachers as well. They are knowledgeable and skilled facilitators in the creation of competent human resources and digitally literate individuals. Thus, experience and instruction can lead to proficiency in the use of technical tools and equipment. Experimentation must be incorporated into instructional methods, and technological tools and equipment must be readily available. (Sotomayor, 2021)

Developing students' technological literacy seems to be important for many aspects of the teaching profession, such as developing lesson plans. Teachers' decisions to include technology into teaching and learning activities are influenced by their beliefs about the best ways to teach the subject as well as their abilities to manage classroom activities using digital tools and devices. Teachers must therefore be able to apply the technological knowledge and skills necessary for professional work duties and obligations if they are to meet the expected outputs.

The main effect of COVID-19 is the requirement for strict social or physical seclusion in order to stop or lessen the virus's transmission. In the case of the Department of Education (DepEd), this meant that for the remaining weeks of the school year 2019–2020, classes and other school-related activities would not be held. In the case of the school year 2020–2021, schools would need to figure out how to continue teaching and learning in the face of the threat and uncertainty posed by COVID-19, all the while protecting the health, safety, and well-being of all students, instructors, and Department staff. The Department of Education's various units and field offices, the Philippine Forum for Inclusive Quality Basic Education, also known as Educ Forum, and the chairs of the House and Senate committees on basic education, senator Sherwin Gatchalian and representative Roman Romulo, provided input for the creation of this Basic Education - Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP). The following principles guided the Office of the Secretary in integrating inputs into the BE-LCP: 1) Protect learners' health, safety, and well-being, and stop the spread of COVID-19; 2) Ensure learning continuity through curriculum adjustments for grades K–12, learning material alignment, multiple learning delivery modalities, corresponding training for teachers and school administrators, and proper orientation for parents or guardians of learners; 3) Facilitate the safe return of teaching and non-teaching personnel and learners to workplaces and schools, taking into account the scenarios projected by the Department of Health (DOH) and the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases in the Philippines

(IATF), supported by additional reliable sources and counterbalanced with DepEd's own risk assessments; 4) Be mindful of equity issues and concerns and make every effort to resolve them; and 5) To make them well-informed decisions, the Department examined basic education data and the epidemiological picture for the upcoming school year when designing the BE-LCP.

In view of this, DepEd has scheduled the start of SY 2020–2021 for August 24, 2020, giving ample time to make the required preparations for the incredibly demanding academic year. The K–12 Curriculum's simplification into the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) and the acceptance of various learning delivery modalities, such as blended and distance learning, either in addition to or instead of in-person instruction, are the main components of the learning strategies that will operationalize the BE–LCP. Self-Learning Modules (SLMs), for use in the upcoming school year, will be made available in print and offline/online digital formats to assist students, parents, and instructors in implementing various learning delivery modalities.

The information, skills, attitudes, and values that comprise the learning outcomes would be evaluated via summative assessments when circumstances permit and a portfolio or electronic portfolio that includes written works and performances (and products), whether in hardcopy or softcopy. National exams would continue to be administered throughout COVID-19.

The United Nations (2020) emphasized that the COVID-19 epidemic has significantly disrupted every aspect of human life, as evidenced by its global spread. Similar to this, the educational industry faced numerous difficulties as traditional schooling gave way to online learning and schools closed to colleges. However, the assertion was backed up by (UNESCO, 2020), which described how this technology shift affected the education of almost half of all students worldwide. Consequently, the COVID-19 epidemic changed education from a traditional paradigm to an online one, which was a novel experience for educators and students alike. The current situation means that teachers need to update their skills and that technology integration in the classroom is becoming more and more vital.

Because of the requirement to implement "emergency remote education" as a result of COVID-19, the educational integration of information and communication technologies (ICT) has been put to the test. In this context of uncertainty, flexible education is an option for promoting a more just, equitable, accessible, and creative educational system. In order to properly interpret the effects of this unique educational circumstance, it is necessary to examine the previous situation in terms of the use of digital technologies in teaching practices.

As a result, the scenario highlights the significance of technology integration in education. Teachers must therefore update their competencies to provide high-quality instruction and adapt their curricula and methods accordingly. Though teachers and students are accustomed to using conventional technological teaching aids like PowerPoint and Smartboards when utilizing information, communication, and technology (ICT) in the classroom, their employability in the real world is still necessary for the methods of instruction.

The capacity to utilize technology to communicate effectively and professionally, organize information, develop high-quality goods, and improve thinking abilities is referred to as technology competency. Technology competence in the classroom refers to a teacher's capacity to use technology to teach and facilitate, as well as improve learning, productivity, and performance. These skills are required to function in today's technology society. Teachers with technology proficiency can discover and investigate a wide range of technical tools and gadgets in order to determine and select the ones that best respond to teaching and learning content. It is essential for educators working in the twenty-first century to include technology into the curriculum for a number of reasons.

In order for students to participate in the global marketplace, they must be exposed to, knowledgeable about, and capable of integrating technologies into dynamic social situations. Technology permeates every aspect of life, and students need to be equipped with 21st-century abilities in order to succeed. Technology competence also increases facilitation and teaching effectiveness. greater time and greater room for planning, creativity, invention, discussion, and ingenuity are all benefits of increased efficiency for educators. Using technology can help teachers become more productive.

With the above cited reviews, the researcher is urge to explore his research study on the technological proficiencies among the science teachers and how these proficiencies influence their performance amid Covid 19. Thus, being confronted with technological know-how, the researcher would like to help the teachers through a learning development program where technical and pedagogical skills are strengthened.

Research Questions

This study attempted to determine the technological proficiency of science teachers and their performance during Covid 19 pandemic which can be a basis for the development of professional program during the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the technological proficiency level of science teachers and administrators based on self-assessment in terms of the following aspects:
 - 1.1. technology operations and concepts;
 - 1.2. planning and designing learning environments and experiences;
 - 1.3. assessment and evaluation;

- 1.4. productivity and professional practice; and
- 1.5. ethical, legal, and human issues?
2. Is there a significant difference between the assessments of the two groups of respondents on the aforementioned aspects?
3. What is the level of science teachers' performance based on their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) during the School Year 2020 – 2021?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the technological proficiency and IPCRF performance of teachers?
5. Based on the study results, what professional development program could be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized the descriptive research method and involved collections of quantitative information that can be tabulated along a continuum in numerical form.

According to McNeill (2018) descriptive method is a methodology that is not exclusive to market researchers but one that can apply to a variety of research methods used in healthcare, psychology, and education.

Descriptive study is to characterize the features or behavior of a group of people. It can incorporate quantitative data even if it isn't based on statistics and tends to favor more qualitative methods. When it comes to a specific group of people, the goal of descriptive research is to describe, explain, or validate some form of hypothesis or objective.

This study used the descriptive research design because it precisely and analytically describes a population, the diverse characteristics, situation or phenomenon. Thus, the study investigated one or more variables to determine its effectiveness.

Respondents

The main sources of data in this study were the science teachers and school administrators in all public junior high school in district I, Schools Division Office-Marikina. The forty (40) science teachers and forty (40) school administrators of the said school served as the research participants of this study.

The purposive sampling was used to determine the exact frequency and percentage of the total respondents per school as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents by School*

School	Science Teachers		School Administrators	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1. Marikina Science High School	5	12.50	5	12.50
2. Barangka NHS	5	12.50	5	12.50
3. Malanday NHS	5	12.50	5	12.50
4. Tañong HS	5	12.50	5	12.50
5. Jesus Dela Peña NHS	5	12.50	5	12.50
6. Kalumpang NHS	5	12.50	5	12.50
7. San Roque NHS	5	12.50	5	12.50
8. Sta. Elena HS	5	12.50	5	12.50
Total	40	100%	40	100%

Instrument

The survey instrument was created and developed by the researcher with aid of the previous studies and aligned with the statement of the problem. The instrument underwent the validation process to ensure such indicators were aligned with the cited variables. The Technological Proficiency Survey Questionnaire (TPSQ) had two elements. The first element talked about the respondents' proficiency level on the technological proficiency in using technological application tools. Then, the second element of the survey focused on the teachers' performance – the Individual Performance Commitment Review form. This was a data-based information and shall be requested from the school records. The survey instrument utilized the five-point Likert scale with its verbal interpretation of Highly Proficient (HP), Proficient (P), Moderately Proficient (MP) Slightly Proficient (SP) and Not Proficient (NP) shown in Table 2.

Table 2. *Scale, Range and Verbal Interpretation*

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50 – 5.00	Highly Proficient
4	3.50 – 4.49	Proficient
3	2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Proficient
2	1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Proficient
1	1.00 – 1.49	Not Proficient

Procedure

To arrive at the aim of the study, the following steps were undertaken: The researcher sought the approval to conduct the study from the schools division office of Marikina. The researcher sought the permission of Schools Division Superintendent of Marikina. After the approval from the Schools Division Superintendent, the researcher asked the principals’ approval in order for him to conduct the study to the school respondents. The approved questionnaire was then administered and then tallied. This was brought to the college statistician. The statistical computations made by the statistician was the source in the breakdown and construal of data. The data transcribed into a manuscript and was presented to the thesis committee for evaluation and approval. The manuscript was revised and presented to the dean of the institute of graduate studies for acceptance.

More so, the researcher considered such ethical considerations by making all the data gathered confidential and requiring permissions from the authorities concerned prior to the gathering of data necessary for the study.

Data Analysis

To treat the gathered data, the following were the statistical tools used:

Weighted Mean. This was applied to described the technological proficiency level of science teachers and administrators based on self-assessment.

Pearson r Coefficient. This was utilized to measure relationship between the technological proficiency and IPCRF performance of teachers.

Table 3. *Range of Correlation Coefficient and Strength of Relationship*

<i>Range</i>	<i>Strength of Relationships</i>
0.00	No correlation
±0.01 to ±0.20	Very low correlation
±0.21 to ±0.40	Slight or Weak correlation
±0.41 to ±0.70	Moderate correlation
±0.71 to ±0.90	High correlation
±0.91 to ±0.99	Very high correlation
±1.00	Perfect correlation

z Test. This was used to see if there was a significant difference between the two groups of respondents' assessments of their technological proficiency.

Correlated t test. This was utilized to examine the significant relationship between the technological proficiency and IPCRF performance of teachers.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data gathered in this study.

Technological Proficiency Level of Science Teachers and Administrators Based on Self-Assessment

The level of technological proficiency of science teachers as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators are shown in Tables 4 to 9.

Technology Operations and Concepts. Table 4 displays the weighted means and verbal interpretation of the respondents' evaluations of the science teachers' and school administrators' assessments of their own technological ability in terms of technology ideas and operations.

It is evident from the table that science teachers' overall weighted means of 3.95 and 4.18, with standard deviations of 0.58 and 0.52, respectively, indicate that they have a Proficient (P) level of technological proficiency as evaluated by both the science teachers and the school administrators in terms of technology operations and concepts. This means that the technological proficiency among science teachers in technological operations and emergent concepts in technology is high. Hence, the respondents have demonstrated their familiarity and skills on effective use of computer operations, information technologies, ethical and legal concerns on the utilization of technology through the aid of software and computer related tasks.

Table 4. *Assessments on the Technological Level Proficiency as to Technology Operations and Concepts*

	<i>Technology Operations and Concepts</i>	<i>Respondents</i>			
		<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Administrators</i>	
		<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	demonstrate effective use of a computer system and utilize computer software.	3.93	P	4.13	P
2.	utilize electronic technologies for information access and sharing.	3.98	P	4.25	P
3.	show that you understand the moral and legal implications of using technology.	3.85	P	4.18	P
4.	use electronic technologies to access and exchange information.	3.98	P	4.25	P
5.	utilize educational technology to support problem solving, decision making,	4.03	P	4.10	P

communication, presentation, data gathering, and information management across the curriculum.

	Overall Weighted Mean	3.95	P	4.18	P
	Standard Deviation	0.58		0.52	

Note: 1.00-1.49, Not Proficient; 1.50-2.49, Slightly Proficient; 2.50-3.49, Moderately Proficient; 3.50-4.49, Proficient; 4.50-5.00, Highly Proficient; WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; P – Proficient

Thus, both groups of respondents believed that technological proficiency as to technology operations and concepts played a crucial aspect in teaching science among learners amid the COVID-19 pandemic. The necessity to learn and improve these proficiencies may lead to an effective and efficient science teacher.

The above results strengthened the claim of Akram et. al. (2021) where the COVID-19 pandemic significantly shifted education from traditional to an online version, which was an emergent state for teachers and students. The substantive situation thus raises the importance of technology integration in education, and teachers are required to update their competencies, respectively.

Thus, it implied that there is a necessity to attend a professional learning program where technology operations and concepts are highly deliberated.

Planning and Designing Learning Environment and Experiences. The weighted means and verbal interpretation of the respondents’ assessments on the level of technological proficiency of science teachers as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators in terms of technology operations and concepts is shown in Table 5.

It can be seen in the table that the level of technological proficiency of science teachers as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators in terms of planning and designing learning environment and experiences is Proficient (P) as shown by the overall weighted means of 3.73 and 4.00 with its standard deviations of 0.65 respectively.

This implies that proficiency skills of the science teachers in technology relative to planning and designing learning environment and experiences in the classroom is high. Thus, the science teachers have designed, applied, identified and planned technology learning resources and managed technological learning resources and enhanced instructional techniques to support the learning needs of the learners in science education.

Further, both groups of respondents believed that the capability of the science teachers in planning and designing learning environment was demonstrated as it plays a critical aspect in the learning development of science teachers amid the covid 19 pandemic where utilization and application of technology learning resources and techno-enhanced learning environment are highlighted.

Table 5. Respondents’ Assessments on the Level of Technological Proficiency as to Planning and Designing Learning Environment and Experiences

	Planning and Designing Learning Environment and Experiences	Respondents			
		Teachers		Administrators	
		WM	VI	WM	VI
1.	design developmentally appropriate learning opportunities that apply technology-enhanced instructional strategies to support the diverse needs of learners.	3.85	P	4.05	P
2.	apply current research on teaching and learning with technology when planning learning environments and experiences.	3.50	P	3.90	P
3.	identify and locate technology resources and evaluate them for accuracy and suitability.	3.70	P	3.98	P
4.	plan for the management of technology resources within the context of learning activities.	3.85	P	4.05	P
5.	plan strategies to manage student learning in a technology-enhanced environment.	3.75	P	4.03	P
Overall Weighted Mean		3.73	P	4.00	P
Standard Deviation		0.65		0.65	

Note: 1.00-1.49, Not Proficient; 1.50-2.49, Slightly Proficient; 2.50-3.49, Moderately Proficient; 3.50-4.49, Proficient; 4.50-5.00, Highly Proficient; WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; P – Proficient

The further results highlighted and supported by the study of Sinakou et. al. (2019) as stressed that to create powerful instructional settings which help students to gain knowledge and skills, we should take into account the current understanding of instructional design. In the field of learning and instruction research, there is now a broad consensus that effective learning occurs when learning environments are ‘powerful’ stimulating learning which is “constructive, cumulative, self-regulated, goal-oriented, situated, collaborative’ and taking into account ‘individually different process of meaning construction and knowledge building.

It implied that science teachers need to collaborate or attend a professional learning development program that highlights planning and designing learning environment and experiences.

Assessment and Evaluation. The weighted means and verbal interpretation of the respondents’ assessments on the level of technological proficiency of science teachers as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators in terms of assessment and evaluation is shown in Table 6.

It can be gleaned in Table 6 that the level of technological proficiency of science teachers as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators in terms of assessment and evaluation is Proficient (P) as evidenced by the overall weighted means of

3.71 and 3.93 with its standard deviations of 0.57 and 0.62 respectively.

This means that proficiency skills of the science teachers in technology relative to assessment and evaluation is high. Consequently, the science teachers have provided useful information, gave real time assessments feedbacks among learners and techno-based assessment have been demonstrated. Thus, the results suggest that there is a necessity to strengthen their proficiency particularly in conducting experiments utilizing the mobile devices.

Furthermore, both the science teachers and the school administrators believed that the competence of the science teachers in assessment and evaluation during Covid 19 pandemic was demonstrated as it plays an important piece in knowledge acquisition and development among science teachers amid Covid 19 wherein giving assessments and evaluations to measure learners' learning are emphasized.

Table 6. Respondents' Assessments on the Level of Technological Proficiency as to Assessment and Evaluation

	Assessment and Evaluation	Respondents			
		Teachers		Administrators	
		WM	VI	WM	VI
1.	provide useful information that can measure processes and outcomes and answer evaluation questions	3.83	P	4.05	P
2.	conduct experiments using mobile devices	3.48	MP	3.75	P
3.	provide Real-Time assessment feedbacks	3.78	P	3.95	P
4.	adapt to learner ability and techno-knowledge	3.85	P	3.90	P
5.	embed technology-based assessments and evaluation in class	3.60	P	3.98	P
Overall Weighted Mean		3.71	P	3.93	P
Standard Deviation		0.57		0.62	

Note: 1.00-1.49, Not Proficient; 1.50-2.49, Slightly Proficient; 2.50-3.49, Moderately Proficient; 3.50-4.49, Proficient; 4.50-5.00, Highly Proficient; WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; P – Proficient

Thus, this supports the study of Canuto et. al. (2024) as they disclosed that the science teachers strongly agreed that professionalism is the most common teaching competence influencing their performance through assessments and evaluation, indicating their adherence to local and national standards and code of conduct. Hence, teachers also strongly agreed with teaching effectiveness, personal skills, educational planning, and management skills towards themselves and for learners.

This implied that it is imperative to collaborate with a school of learning professionals through a professional training relative to assessment and evaluation learning concepts ad ideas.

Productivity and Professional Practice. The weighted means and verbal interpretation of the respondents' assessments on the level of technological proficiency of science teachers as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators in terms of productivity and professional practice is shown in Table 7.

It can be gleaned in Table 7 that the level of technological proficiency of science teachers as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators in terms of productivity and professional practice is Proficient (P) as evidenced by the overall weighted means of 3.81 and 4.02 with its standard deviations of 0.57 and 0.54 respectively.

This means that proficiency of the science teachers in technology relative to productivity and professional practice is high. Subsequently, the science teachers have utilized, evaluated and modeled advanced features of word processing tool, publishing desktop and utilization of graphical software programs have been proved. More so, the science teachers have technology to communicate and collaborate with both the learners and the colleagues during the Covid 19 pandemic.

Table 7. Respondents' Assessments on the Level of Technological Proficiency as to Productivity and Professional Practice

	Productivity and Professional Practice	Respondents			
		Teachers		Administrators	
		WM	VI	WM	VI
1.	use technology resources to engage in ongoing professional development and lifelong learning.	3.83	P	3.98	P
2.	evaluate and reflect on professional practice to make informed decisions regarding the use of technology in support of student learning	3.80	P	4.00	P
3.	apply technology to increase productivity.	3.90	P	4.08	P
4.	use technology to communicate and collaborate with peers, parents, and the larger community in order to nurture student learning.	3.98	P	4.10	P
5.	model advanced features of word processing, desktop publishing, graphics programs, and utilities to develop professional products.	3.55	P	3.93	P
Overall Weighted Mean		3.81	P	4.02	P
Standard Deviation		0.57		0.54	

Note: 1.00-1.49, Not Proficient; 1.50-2.49, Slightly Proficient; 2.50-3.49, Moderately Proficient; 3.50-4.49, Proficient; 4.50-5.00, Highly Proficient; WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; P – Proficient

The results were supported by Panoy et. al. (2022) where COVID-19 has imposed changes to the educational system shifting from

conventional classroom setting to online learning. Assessing students' proficiency with technology and expectations for online learning are vital for their success.

Additionally, both the science teachers and the school administrators believed that the ability of the science teachers in productivity and professional practice during the COVID-19 pandemic was established, as it plays an important element in knowledge acquisition and professional practice in teaching among science teachers, wherein the use of productivity software programs is accentuated.

Social, Ethical, Legal and Human Issues. The weighted means and verbal interpretation of the respondents' assessments on the level of technological proficiency of science teachers as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators in terms of social, ethical, legal and human issues is shown in Table 8.

It can be seen in the table that the level of technological proficiency of science teachers as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators in terms of social, ethical, legal and human issues is Proficient (P) as shown by the overall weighted means of 3.71 and 4.00 with its standard deviations of 0.68 and 0.67 respectively. This implies that proficiency level of the science teachers in technology relative to social, ethical, legal and human issues is high. Thus, the science teachers have modeled legal and practice ethical technological usage and applied these technological resources among diverse learners with their respective characters and background.

Table 8. Respondents' Assessments on the Level of Technological Proficiency as to Social, Ethical, Legal, and Human Issues

	Social, Ethical, Legal, and Human Issues	Respondents			
		Teachers		Administrators	
		WM	VI	WM	VI
1.	model and teach legal and ethical practice related to technology use.	3.53	P	3.90	P
2.	apply technology resources to enable and empower learners with diverse backgrounds, characteristics, and abilities.	3.73	P	4.00	P
3.	identify and use technology resources that affirm diversity.	3.68	P	3.98	P
4.	promote safe and healthy use of technology resources.	3.88	P	4.10	P
5.	facilitate equitable access to technology resources for all students.	3.75	P	4.00	P
Overall Weighted Mean		3.71	P	4.00	P
Standard Deviation		0.68		0.67	

Note: 1.00-1.49, Not Proficient; 1.50-2.49, Slightly Proficient; 2.50-3.49, Moderately Proficient; 3.50-4.49, Proficient; 4.50-5.00, Highly Proficient; WM – Weighted Mean; VI – Verbal Interpretation; P – Proficient

The result was supported by Dwivedi, Y. (2023) where technology presents opportunities as well as, often ethical and legal, challenges, and has the potential for both positive and negative impacts for organizations, society, and individuals.

Moreover, both the science teachers and the school administrators believed that the capacity of the science teachers in using technology relative to social, ethical, legal and human issues during the COVID-19 pandemic was promoted and facilitated as it serves as a vital component in skills and social practice in teaching wherein legal use and human concerns are stressed.

The summary of the weighted means and verbal interpretation of the respondents' assessments on the level of technological proficiency of science teachers as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators is shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Summary of Respondents' Assessments on the Level of Technological Proficiency

Aspects	Respondents				
	Teachers		Administrators		
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	
1.	Technology operations and concepts	3.95	P	4.18	P
2.	Planning and Designing learning environments and experiences	3.73	P	4.00	P
3.	Assessment and evaluation	3.71	P	3.93	P
4.	Productivity and professional practice	3.81	P	4.02	P
5.	Social, ethical, legal, and human issues	3.71	P	4.00	P
Grand Weighted Mean		3.78	P	4.03	P

Note: OWM – Overall Weighted Mean

It can be seen in the table that the level of technological proficiency of science teachers as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators is high as evidenced by the grand weighted means of 3.78 and 4.03 respectively.

This implies that the proficiency level of the science teachers in technology relative to the above cited five aspects is high. Thus, the skills of the science teachers in utilizing technology and concepts, planning and designing, using different assessments and evaluations, productivity tools and professional practice are highly evident.

Test of Significant Difference Between the Assessments of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Technological Proficiency

Tables 10 to 15 presents the computed z values and critical t values on the science teachers' level of technological proficiency as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators.

Technology Operations and Concepts. Tables 10 presents the computed z value and critical t value on the science teachers' level of technological proficiency as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators as regards technology operations and concepts.

As evident in Table 10, the computed z value of 1.87 is lesser than the critical z value of 1.96. This indicates that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected at a 5% level of significance. As a result, there is no significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the technological proficiency level in terms of technology operations and concepts.

Table 10. *Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Technological Proficiency as regards Technology Operations and Concepts*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	40	3.95	0.58	1.87	1.96	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Administrators	40	4.18	0.52				

Note: n – Sample Size s – Standard Deviation H₀ – Null Hypothesis $\alpha = 5\%$

This implies that both the science teachers and the school administrators have similar assessments on the level of technological proficiency of science teachers as regards technology operations and concepts. Thus, the way the science teachers see technological operations and concepts does not significantly differ from the school administrators' assessment on how science teachers' proficiency in technological operations and concepts manifests.

Planning and Designing Learning Environments and Experiences. Tables 11 presents the computed z value and critical t value on the science teachers' level of technological proficiency as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators as regards planning and designing learning environments and experiences.

As reflected in Table 11, the computed z value of 1.86 is below the critical z value of 1.96. So, at a 5% significance level the statistical decision is to fail to reject the null hypothesis.

This suggests that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the technological proficiency level in terms of planning and designing learning environments and experiences.

Table 11. *Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Technological Proficiency as regards Planning and Designing Learning Environments and Experiences*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	40	3.73	0.65	1.86	1.96	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Administrators	40	4.00	0.65				

Note: n – Sample Size s – Standard Deviation H₀ – Null Hypothesis $\alpha = 5\%$

This means that the science teachers themselves and the school administrators have common assessments of the level of technological proficiency of science teachers. Their claims relative to the technology usage in planning and designing the learning environment and the experiences of the science teachers are the same. Furthermore, the technological proficiency of science teachers in planning and designing technological skills has nothing to do with the way the school administrators have observed science teachers in planning and designing technological skills.

Assessment and Evaluation. Tables 12 presents the computed z value and critical t value on the science teachers' level of technological proficiency as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators as regards assessments and evaluations.

Table 12 displayed that the computed z value of 1.66 is smaller than the critical z value of 1.96. Therefore, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis at a 5% level of significance.

This shows that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the technological proficiency level in terms of assessment and evaluation.

This implies that the two groups of respondents had similar assessments on how science teachers' technological proficiency has been demonstrated in terms of providing assessments and giving evaluations to learners.

Table 12. *Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Technological Proficiency as regards Assessment and Evaluation*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	40	3.71	0.57	1.66	1.96	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Administrators	40	3.93	0.62				

Note: n – Sample Size s – Standard Deviation H0 – Null Hypothesis α = 5%

Hence, the way the science teachers assessed themselves in technological proficiency relative to assessments and evaluations doesn't have an impact on the way the school administrators have assessed the technological skills of the science teachers as far as assessments and evaluations are concerned.

Productivity and Professional Practice. Tables 13 presents the computed z value and critical t value on the science teachers' level of technological proficiency as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators as regards productivity and professional practice.

It can be observed in Table 13 that the computed z value of 1.65 is less than the critical z value of 1.96. At a 5% level of significance, this implies that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. As a result, there is no significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the technological proficiency level in terms of productivity and professional practice.

This means that the assessment of the science teacher respondents on the level of their technology proficiency as regards productivity and professional practice was the same. Hence, both of them have similarly seen how technology management was demonstrated by the science teachers.

Table 13. Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Technological Proficiency as regards Productivity and Professional Practice

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	40	3.81	0.57	1.65	1.96	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Administrators	40	4.02	0.54				

Note: n – Sample Size s – Standard Deviation H0 – Null Hypothesis α = 5%

Moreso, the competence in technology of science teachers in productivity and professional practice does not significantly vary from what the school administrators' assessments of the science teacher's technological proficiency relative to the above-cited variable.

Social, Ethical, Legal, and Human Issues. Tables 14 presents the computed z value and critical t value on the science teachers' level of technological proficiency as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators as regards social, ethical, legal and human issues.

Table 14 exhibited that the computed z value of 1.92 is below the critical z value of 1.96. Hence, at a 5% level of significance the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. This supports that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the technological proficiency level in terms of social, ethical, legal, and human issues.

Table 14. Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Technological Proficiency as regards Social, Ethical, Legal, and Human Issues

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed z Value	Critical z value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	40	3.71	0.68	1.92	1.96	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Administrators	40	4.00	0.67				

Note: n – Sample Size s – Standard Deviation H0 – Null Hypothesis α = 5%

This means that the two groups of respondents have assessed the technological proficiency of science teachers relative to social, ethical, legal, and human issues the same. Thus, they both agreed and claimed that the social, ethical, legal, and human issues of science teachers have been established. Likewise, the school administrator's assessment of technological proficiency in the matter of social, ethical, legal, and human issues doesn't matter on what the science teachers have assessed by themselves.

Tables 15 presents the summary of computed z values and critical t values on the science teachers' level of technological proficiency as assessed by the science teachers themselves and the school administrators as regards social, ethical, legal and human issues.

As depicted in Table 15, the assessments of science teachers and school administrator respondents on the level of technological proficiency pertaining to technology operations and concepts; planning and designing learning environments and experiences; assessment and evaluation; productivity and professional practice; and social, ethical, legal, and human issues do not show significant difference as presented in the respective computed z values which are smaller than the critical z values. This implies that the respondents' assessments are similar.

Table 15. Summary of Test of Significant Difference in the Assessment of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Level of Technological Proficiency

Aspects	Teachers		Administrators		Computed z Value	Decision	Interpretation
	OWM	s	OWM	s			
a. Technology operations and concepts	3.95	0.58	4.18	0.52	1.87	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
b. Planning and Designing learning environments and experiences	3.73	0.65	4.00	0.65	1.86	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant

c.	Assessment and evaluation	3.71	0.57	3.93	0.62	1.66	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
d.	Productivity and professional practice	3.81	0.57	4.02	0.54	1.65	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
e.	Social, ethical, legal, and human issues	3.71	0.68	4.00	0.67	1.92	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant

This also suggests that both the science teachers and the school administrators have agreed on the way they assessed the science teachers’ technological proficiency, which plays a significant skill to be acquired and used while dealing with learners in this time of health crisis—the COVID-19 pandemic.

This implied that there is a necessity for science teachers to attend such trainings that would highlight technological proficiency in order to augment their performance.

Level of Science Teachers’ Performance Based on Their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) During School Year 2021 – 2022

Table 16 presents the level of science teachers’ performance based on their Individual Performance Commitment and Review (IPCRF) for during the School Year 2021-2022.

It can be seen in the table that the level of performance of the teachers that range from 4.500 to 5.000 was categorized as Outstanding (O) with four (4) or 10%.

A total of thirty-three (33) or 82.5% of teachers were noted to have Very Satisfactory (VS) ratings ranging from 3.500 to 4.499 while three (3) or 7.5% of science teachers was noted to have Satisfactory (S) performance rating ranging 2.500 to 2.499 respectively.

Table 16. *Teachers’ Performance Based on the IPCRF-PPST*

Performance		Frequency	Percentage
Indicator	Range		
Outstanding	4.500 – 5.000	4	10
Very Satisfactory	3.500 – 4.499	33	82.5
Satisfactory	2.500 – 3.499	3	7.5
Unsatisfactory	1.500 – 2.499	0	0
Poor	1.000 – 1.499	0	0
Total		40	100

This result demonstrates that the vast majority of science teachers are doing a fantastic job. Though, there is a necessity to inspire science teachers to improve their teaching performance in order for them to meet the outstanding performance level.

The above claimed was supported by Stanley (2023) as stated that: by encouraging teachers to actively participate in their own education, teacher professional development guarantees that both teachers and students have a strong desire to learn. By offering training and assistance to your teachers, you are conveying to them that the school community appreciates their work and wishes to see them develop. For educators, a dearth of resources for professional development can be depressing. It conveys a lack of interest in investing in the caliber of instruction and increases the pressure on educators to further their professional development.

Test of Significant Relationship Between the Technological Proficiency and Performance of Teachers

The test of the significant relationship between the science teachers’ technological proficiency and the individual performance review form is presented in Tables 17.

Table 17 exposed that the Pearson r coefficients (0.14, 0.01, 0.07, 0.22, and 0.09) between the level of Technological Proficiency and IPCRF Performance of Teachers signifies very low and weak positive correlations.

At a 5% significance level, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis since the computed t values (0.85, 0.08, 0.44, 1.37, and 0.54) are lower than the critical t value (2.02) with 38 degrees of freedom. Thus, there is no significant relationship between the level of Technological Proficiency and IPCRF Performance of Teachers.

Table 17. *Test of Significant Relationship Between the Technological Proficiency and IPCRF Performance of Science Teachers*

	Pearson r	Interpretation	Computed t Value	Critical t Value	Decision	Interpretation
Technology operations and concepts Performance	0.14	Very low	0.85	2.02	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
Planning and Designing learning environments and experiences Performance	0.01	Very low	0.08	2.02	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
Assessment and evaluation Performance	0.07	Very low	0.44	2.02	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
Productivity and professional practice	0.22	Weak	1.37	2.02	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant

Performance						
Social, ethical, legal, and human issues	0.09	Very low	0.54	2.02	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
Performance						

This means that there is no evidence to support the claim that science teachers perform better when their technology ability is assessed as being higher. Furthermore, the performance of the science teachers is not strongly correlated with their technological skill. Therefore, if the science teachers are innovative and technologically advanced, this will not affect how they perform in class.

The results were supported by the claimed of Backfisch et. al. (2021) where integrating technologies into teaching has the potential to both support students' learning and enable them to participate in a digitalized society. However, research has shown that using technologies is not generally effective for supporting teaching and learning processes but rather depends on how they are used during teaching.

Professional Development Program

For science teachers to progress and raise their level of skill, a professional development program in technical proficiency is crucial. Going beyond the usage of these talents, particularly in dealing with school settings and professional support among school colleagues, is the biggest difficulty of this professional program. The process that attempts to give a vision of high-quality teaching and technological integration learning skills development both inside and outside of the school is therefore the one that must be modified the most.

Rationale

As stipulated by Learning A-Z (2023), professional development is an organized kind of professional learning that assists teachers by helping them keep up with developing technology and enhance student learning while also enabling successful, modern classrooms. Partnering with other schools that provide educational technology and who provide help over the whole implementation cycle is crucial for administrators and teachers. Thus, to answer this call, it is in this program proposal that teachers' needs in technological skills shall be addressed so that they have enough knowledge and techno-knowhow in facing the learners regarding technological proficiency advancement and teaching integration.

In the analysis of the data sought from the research participants, the researcher recognized the results of the level of technological proficiency of science teachers. The data revealed that among the five aspects of technological proficiency, the level of the science teacher's proficiency was assessed as "high or proficient". With this result, there's still a necessity for a professional development program in order that these skills of the research participants may be addressed and aimed at increasing to "very high or highly proficient".

Thus, the researcher found out that there is really a need for a development program that would enrich, hone, and improve their skills in technology and use them in their respective schools.

Objectives

The professional development program for science teachers aims to:

Discuss the study results on the science teachers' technological proficiency.

Develop knowledge, skills and attitude of the science teachers in accordance with training standards that would cover the five elements in technological proficiency such as technology operations and concepts; planning and designing learning environments and experiences; assessment and evaluation; productivity and professional practice; and social, ethical, legal, and human issues.

Apply learning skills and show appreciation on the significance of technological proficiency in school learning environment.

Demonstrate knowledge, skills and attitude on the use of technological proficiency in school.

Conclusions

Considering the findings above, the following conclusions are hereby arrived at:

The science teachers and the school administrators have the same assessments on how they observed the science teachers' technological proficiency in the aspects of technology operations and concepts; planning and designing learning environments and experiences; assessment and evaluation; productivity and professional practice; and social, ethical, legal, and human issues.

The assessments of both the science teachers and the school administrators on the technological proficiency of science teachers do not differ significantly.

Majority of the science teachers' level of performance as reflected in IPCRF was noted to be Very Satisfactory.

The technological proficiency of science teachers does not affect their performance.

The professional development program which aims to enhance the technological proficiency of science teachers is needed to address and increase teachers' proficiency level from proficient to a highly proficient.

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are hereby proposed:

It is recommended that the science teachers should attend the professional development program in technological proficiency.

The science teachers should continue their expertise in utilizing technologies and integrate these to their classroom so that their performance would increase from very satisfactory to outstanding.

Technological proficiency is important in school where science teachers and their colleagues will benefit.

A proposed professional development program may be implemented to determine its effectiveness and efficiency.

Researchers are encouraged to study other variables related to technological proficiencies and techno-skills learning.

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